
Review

Depressive Disorder and its Link to Delinquency of Young Adults

Hvala Karin¹

¹ University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Medicine, Ljubljana, Slovenia

* Correspondence: mentor; jakob.misic@gmail.com

Abstract:

There has been a fair share of research done on the link between depression and criminal activity. This article focuses mainly on the depression-criminal activity link in young adults. Can depression be the reason for criminal activity, or is it the result of it? Depression, as defined by WHO, affects around 3.8% of the global population, with adolescents being particularly vulnerable. Studies show a significant connection between depression and delinquency, especially in high-risk groups like incarcerated adolescents, where depression rates are disproportionately high. Research suggests that early depressive symptoms can lead to delinquent behaviours, often exacerbated by factors like poor social standing, substance abuse, and lack of social support. Several studies demonstrate that social support, particularly from siblings and extended family, plays a crucial role in mitigating depression and reducing delinquency. However, peer and parental support may not be as impactful in lowering depressive symptoms. The findings emphasize the need for early mental health interventions and gender-specific approaches, focusing on strengthening family relationships to reduce both depression and delinquent behaviour in vulnerable populations.

Keywords: Depression; Delinquency; Adolescents; Social support; Criminal behaviour; Mental health

1. Introduction

1.1. *Depressive disorder – general characteristics*

Depressive disorders alongside bipolar disorders fall under mood disorders. In any mood disorder the mood is altered for a significant amount of time. Typical for mood disorders is also the repetitiveness of episodes (50 – 70% of patients with major depressive disorder have recurrent episodes), a singular depressive episode is less common. Risk factors for chronicity involve family history of depression, higher age, alcoholism, medical illness and longer period of untreated illness. (Cutler J. L, 2014) Depressive disorders include major depressive disorder, persistent depressive disorder, disruptive mood dysregulation disorder, premenstrual dysphoric disorder, other specified depressive disorders and unspecified depressive disorder. (Cutler J. L, 2014)

Typical for depressive disorders is a depressed mood, sad feelings, often persistently lowered self-esteem or intensified self-criticism, a sense of guilt or inadequacy, intense pessimism and hopelessness, loss of interest or even anhedonia etc. Depression is often accompanied by anxiety, feelings of overwhelm, helplessness and hopelessness.

Depressive disorders are associated with changes in sleep pattern, including insomnia or in 30% of depressed patients hypersomnia. Patients also report a lack of libido and cognitive dysfunction.

Approximately one third of depressed patients have depression with atypical features, such as hypersomnia, hyper appetite. (Cutler J. L, 2014)

According to WHO, depression (or depressive disorder) is defined as a common mental disorder, which includes depressed mood or loss of pleasure or interest in activities for longer periods of time. More likely to develop depression are those who underwent some sort of trauma or stressful situations, who experienced abuse etc. Its occurrence is not limited to a singular population group, it can in fact happen to anyone. (WHO, 2023)

1.2. *Depressive disorder - occurrence*

WHO estimates that 3,8% of population suffers from depression at some time in their life. In the population there is approximately 5% of adults (4% among men, 6 % among women). Another vital group where depression is quite common – more than 10% develop depression - are pregnant women (ante – natal depression) and women who just gave birth (post-natal depression). (WHO, 2023)

The prevalence of depression in adolescence is higher than in early childhood, possibly because of increased social demands, more responsibility and biological changes. A 2015 meta-analysis of 41 studies conducted in 27 countries found that prevalence of mental disorders in adolescents worldwide was 13.4%, with depressive disorders coming up to 2.6%. (Polancyzk G. V., 2015)

2. Depression – Delinquency Link

2.1. *Studies involving marginalised adolescents*

A study conducted in 2000 finds that 25% of 1024 evaluated incarcerated adolescents had moderate depression and 22% had severe depression. The study was conducted in the form of self-administered questionnaires and they focused on depression, drug and alcohol abuse, panic and anxiety disorders. 20% of the depressed young adults were previously diagnosed and treated for depression. (Domalanta D. D., 2003) In 2002, researchers in Illinois, Chicago took a sample of 1829 adolescents, aged 10 – 18, majority of whom were male (1172 males, 657 females) and found that nearly two thirds of males and nearly three quarters of females reached criteria for one or more psychiatric disorders. More than 20% of females reached the criteria for a major depressive episode. (Teplin L. A., 2003)

There is evidence that suggests there is a connection between depressive disorders and criminal activity or youth delinquency. There is a trend of co - occurrence of mental disorders, poor social standing, substance abuse and other factors which contribute to non-socially accepted behaviour. (Ozkan, 2018) It seems depression is not a direct cause for

criminal activity but it is a sure risk factor. Researchers acknowledge that the pool of adolescents included in their study were high risk offenders, which could mean that the results could not be applied to general public. (Ozkan, 2018)

A study by Miklowitz (2014) explores the connection between depression, delinquency, and psychosis among adolescents in foster care, with a focus on the multidimensional treatment foster care (MTFC) program. The research included 166 girls aged 13–17 who had been arrested and placed in foster care, analysing the effectiveness of MTFC compared to standard group care. The study found that depression and delinquency were intertwined, with stress generation being a critical factor. Girls who displayed delinquent behaviour often faced stress, which exacerbated depressive symptoms and negative thinking. Importantly, MTFC helped reduce both delinquent and depressive behaviours by improving the home environment and providing emotional support, suggesting that depression may come first and lead to delinquent behaviours due to emotional withdrawal. The findings indicate that addressing emotional instability and family stress is crucial for reducing delinquency and depression in foster care adolescents.

A study by Kofler et al. (2011) included a nationwide, longitudinal sample of 3,604 adolescents aged 12 to 17 years. The study used a cohort-sequential latent growth curve modelling approach to examine the relationship between depression and delinquency over time. Data was collected through structured telephone interviews. The study aimed to determine whether early depressive symptoms predicted changes in delinquent behaviour or whether early delinquency predicted changes in depressive symptoms. Results showed that early depressive symptoms were a better predictor of age-related increases in delinquency than early delinquency was of depressive symptoms, particularly for girls. The findings support the "acting out" model, suggesting that depression may lead to delinquent behaviour, rather than the reverse.

2.2. Depression and Violent Offences

Fazel et al. (2015) examines the association between depression and violent crime using two complementary Swedish population-based studies. The first study involved 47,158 individuals diagnosed with depression between 2001 and 2009, who were compared with 898,454 general population controls. The results show that individuals with depression had a threefold increased risk of violent crime compared to the general population, even after adjusting for sociodemographic factors and familial confounding. Men with depression had a higher rate of violent offenses (3.7%) compared to women (0.5%). The second study, which included twins (n=23 020), found a significant link between depressive symptoms and violent crime. These results emphasize the need for considering the risk of violence in clinical evaluations of individuals with depression, particularly in certain high-risk subgroups such as those with prior substance abuse or criminal history.

2.3. Depression and a support system

Nowadays the majority of population has the notion that depression is less likely to occur or rather develop in a socially solid environment. Although at first glance this might be true, depression disorders result of various factors, including personality traits. All of this could be applied to young delinquents as well as general society.

Focusing on the relationship between social support and depression in incarcerated adolescents, a study conducted by Johnson J. E. et al in 2010, took a sample of 198 incarcerated adolescents and found that greater support from family and overall satisfaction with support systems predicted lower depression levels for both boys and girls. Notably, support from siblings and extended family had a stronger association with reduced depression, while support from parents or friends had little to no significant effect. Girls reported higher levels of depression and received more support from friends and extended family, but less from parents compared to boys. Family and sibling support were stronger predictors of lower depression in girls than in boys. This study highlights that sibling and extended family support are important but often overlooked resources for emotional well-being in incarcerated teens. Conversely, peer support was less protective against depression, and romantic friend support had no significant effect on depression. The findings suggest that relationships with parents may be less impactful on depression for incarcerated youth than previously thought. These results have important treatment implications, suggesting a need for gender-specific interventions that emphasize strengthening family,

especially sibling, and extended family relationships. The study underscores the importance of addressing social support networks to reduce depression in criminal justice-involved youth. (Johnson J. E., 2010)

3. Conclusions

In conclusion, the connection between depression and delinquency is evident, although complex, with depression serving as a significant risk factor for antisocial behaviour, particularly in vulnerable populations like adolescents. While depression may not directly cause delinquency, it can exacerbate stress and emotional withdrawal, leading to increased risk of non-socially accepted behaviours. It would be interesting to find out which of typical depression characteristics result in higher criminal activity, although inability to isolate a singular symptom of depressive disorders makes it hard to directly link a singular symptom to (higher) criminal activity. Studies highlight the importance of addressing mental health issues early, particularly in high-risk groups such as incarcerated youth, where depression rates are disproportionately high. Social support, especially from siblings and extended family, plays a crucial role in mitigating depressive symptoms and reducing delinquency. Future interventions should prioritize strengthening these support systems and implementing gender-specific approaches to effectively address both depression and delinquent behaviour.

Conflicts of Interest: The author declares no conflict of interest.

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